

Does the Categories of the IPOs Differs the Post Listing Performance Risk? : An Evidence Assessment of Indian SME Financing

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Abstract : *The 'Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyaan' is being greeted as economic revival from a global pandemic, and to restart India's MSMEs (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises). Modi government has announced special packages and offered 15% equity infusion to MSMEs to tap the capital market. Such a move of the government increases the trust of the investors towards the investments in MSMEs. Valuation of such unorganized firms is difficult, hence investments in SME IPOs are highly risky. Volatility refers to the degree of change related to stock price, higher volatility implies a higher risk of investments. Using 187 IPOs listed on NSE Emerge, the present study measures volatility for initial one month from listing. Further, it compares the performance based on issue-specific variables, market-related variables, and company-specific variables. Volatility is found significantly higher for IPOs with higher RNOW, higher subscription ratio, and issued during positive market sentiment.*

Keywords : Initial Return Volatility, SME IPOs, Performance Uncertainty.

Introduction

MSMEs contribute significantly to most countries' economic development and employment. (Stein, Goland & Schiff, 2010). In, the Indian context, MSMEs employ over 11 crores workers, contributes 29% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and encompass nearly fifty percentage of exports. Around 90.19 lakh MSMEs are registered in India and out of which 6.33 crore (99.4 %) are micro-enterprises. The 'Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyaan' is greeted as an important fiscal

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policy to ease India's economic difficulty due to pandemics. 'Atmanirbhar' package to restart India's MSME sector was announced by the Modi government on 13th May 2020. In order to boost the growth of MSMEs, the government has planned to provide 15% equity infusion to those who want to take finance through a public listing. The idea is to hold the funds for 2-3 years in MSMEs and sell the same when it appreciates and uses the funds in reinvesting in another encouraging MSME. The government has kept Rs 50,000 crore as a rolling fund, which will be continuously invested.

Access to finance is the biggest challenge for exponential growth of MSMEs. In the global competitive market, to compete against Chinese products, MSMEs exposure towards the capital market becomes essential. A public listing of SMEs provides growth and liquidity to investors and employees holding ESOPs and exit routes to private equity investors. In India, BSE SME and NSE Emerge, established in 2012, provide SMEs a public listing opportunity with least compliances and cost compared to the mainboard exchange. NSE Emerge and BSE SME exchange has raised 6481.22 cores since its inception to December 2019 by successfully issuing 524 SME IPOs (Source: Handbook of Statistics_2019, SEBI). During the pandemic situation of Covid19, 20 SME IPOs have successfully raised 120.07 crores from March to October 2020.

Regulations for listing at SME exchanges are significantly different than mainboard IPOs listing. Listing at SME exchanges is exempted from SEBI approval, in-principal approval of stock exchanges, and public notice requirements. Hence, the risk associated with the SME investment increases, and assessing the same becomes very important. Volatility refers to the degree of change related to stock price, higher volatility implies that a security's share price can possibly be accelerate in any direction, while less volatility implies a more stable price. The higher volatility indicates that security is riskier. Volatility is often assessed as the standard deviation which helps to identify stocks for successful investing. The present study contributes by measuring the volatility of SME IPOs India listed on NSE Emerge since its inception in the year 2012 and comparing based on various company, issue, and market-specific variables.

Literature Review

Volatility is the standard deviation of the first 30 days post listing of IPOs (Mcguinness, 2016); while for 20 trading days post listing (Sahoo, 2014b; Sahoo, 2015). Listing day volatility is the distinction between high price and low price scaled by amount of high price and low price (Sahoo, 2014a). Fundamentally

strong IPO stocks minimizes the post listing performance risk (Sahoo, 2017). Hong Kong IPOs evidenced initial period volatility of 5.361 percent and 30-day volatility of 3.563 percent (Mcguinness, 2016). Indian IPOs evidenced 0.17 percent of volatility (Sahoo, 2014a); while volatility of 12.52 percent (Sahoo, 2014b); 0.15 percent listing day volatility, and 18.03 percent 20 days post (Sahoo, 2015).

Older firms are considered as established firms that possess a lower extent of risk (Ritter, 1991). Pre-IPO profitability provides information about the business prospects, and superior information reduces performance risk (Welch, 1989). Oversubscription ratio and volatility are positively associated (Vong, 2006). Higher level of post listing volatility for the firms associated with reputable investment bank underwriters, firms backed by venture capital, firms listed on the NASDAQ stock exchange, lower levels of debt, belongs to the technology sector listed during the period with high market volatility (Gleason, Johnston & Madura, 2008).

Underpricing, market sentiment, and float size effects initial return volatility; IPOs with a large offer size, reduce the offer price spreads and the reputation of underwriters leading to less volatility (Mcguinness, 2016). Listing day returns are affected by the volume of informed investors, while the volume of uninformed investors accelerates post listing volatility (Abraham, Harris & Auerbach, 2016). Analyst favourable recommendation reduces listing day volatility (Sahoo, 2014a). IPO firms' board diversity and reputation and a large number of outside directors shrink aftermarket IPO price volatility; venture capital-backed IPOs are less volatile for the short-run (Sahoo, 2014b). Subscription rate gives a compelling sign to assessing both listing and post-listing price variability; larger issues have reported less volatility (Sahoo, 2015). IPOs are more transparent and likely to be less volatile with the participation from anchor investors, where as the market condition emphatically increases the volatility (Sahoo, 2017).

Based on the detailed review of literature, the present study tries to fulfil the gap by following ways. **First**, the study is focused on the SME Exchange of India with the recent dataset, sample of IPOs listed on NSE EMERGE from its inception from the year 2012 to August 2019 to uncover volatility up to 30 days of listing. **Second**, the study **compares** the magnitude of volatility for issue, company, and market-specific variables.

Objectives of the Study

The present study has twofold objectives; 1) is to measure the performance of IPOs listed on NSE Emerge in terms of volatility and 2) To compare post listing volatility of 10, 20, 30 day regularly issues company and market specific variables.

Rationale

The government encourages the capital market route for MSMEs to overcome the pandemic situation of Covid-19, by providing 15% equity infusion of up to Rs.50000 crores. The pricing and performance of SME IPOs play a significant in the future interest of investors, issuers, and regulators. The present study encompasses a new segment of the volatility of post listing, which is an important but not researched area. The findings would have suggestions for the issuers, investors and regulators.

Data and Methodology

Sample Selection

The sample data for this study consists of all the IPOs that were listed on the NSE Emerge stock exchange from its inception in September 2012 to August 2019. Table-1 outlines the sample for the study. Data has been collected from various sources such as <https://www.nseindia.com/emerge/>, Capitaline Plus Software, NIFTY Small Cap 250 Index data collected from <https://www.nseindia.com/>, and few variables collected from <https://www.chittorgarh.com/>.

Table-1 : Details of Sample

Sample period September 2012 to August 2019	
Particulars	Number of IPOs
Total number of IPOs issued during sample period	196
Excluded : Traded less than 30 days from listing	7
Finance and Investment Sector Firms	2
Final Sample Size	187
Sample as percentage of total IPOs	95.41%

Source : Primary data.

Description of Variables

This study measures the IPO volatility post one month of listing and further evaluates the difference in IPO performance with different categories. Variables mentioned below are included in the study based on significance proved in the earlier studies.

Dependent Variable : After Market Price Risk (Volatility)

Assessment of price risk (price variability) indicates the quality of IPOs. IPOs with higher price variability are considered riskier than the less price variability. The study uses Sahoo's (2017) extreme value measure for volatility measurement. The study measures the volatility i.e. risk as the natural log high price divided by the low price on listing day. Listing day volatility is termed as Vol, and simple average Vol for first 10, 20, and 30 days post listing are termed as Vol_10d, Vol_20d, and Vol_30d. Risk and volatility are used interchangeably.

Description of Categories

Table-2 enlist the definition of variables, and for the comparison based on Age, CFO_TA, PIPH, RNOW, DE, share premium, listing delay, risk factors, subscription times, offer size; the sample of 187 IPOs have been classified into four quartiles based upon the lower value (Q1) to a high value (Q4). And for market sentiment, the sample has been divided into two categories, positive and negative market sentiments.

Table-2 : Definition of Variables

Variables	Definition
CATEGORY-1 : Company Specific Variables	
Age	Age of the firm is defined as number of years between incorporation and IPO listing.
CFO_TA	Operating cashflow during the financial year immediately preceding the IPO, scaled by total assets of the firm is encompassed as CFO_TA.
PIPH	Percentage of equity ownership held by the promoter; post-IPO defined as PIPH.
RNOW	Ratio of profit after tax to net worth in the financial year immediately preceding the IPO is defined as RNOW.

DE	Debt to equity capital ratio (book value) in the financial year immediately preceding the IPO is considered as DE.
CATEGORY-2 : Issue Specific Variables	
Share Premium	Present study defines the share premium as the ratio of offer price to face value
Listing Delay	Listing delay is considered as a number of days between listing day and offer closing day.
Risk Factors	Number of Risk Factors mentioned in the IPO prospectus
Subscription Times	Subscription times are defined as the number of times the overall IPO is over subscribed measured as the ratio of the total number of shares applied to the number of shares offered.
Offer Size	Offer Size is defined as IPO offer price multiplied with number of shares issued.
CATEGORY-3 : Market Specific Variables	
Market Sentiment	Nifty Small Cap 250 index average daily return during 30 trading days preceding the IPO opening is encompassed as market index return.

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Empirical Results and Analysis

Extent of IPO Performance : Volatility

The performance of SME IPOs is depicted in Table-3. The volatility of 187 SME IPOs issued during the period is depicted with the minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation values. Listing day volatility ratio (vol) is evidenced mean 0.08, and declined to 0.05 for average 10 days volatility, 0.04 for 20 and 30 days post listing. The minimum values for the volatility ratio are 0.00 throughout the period, which indicates no variability of price. Maximum of volatility is highest on a listing day, then declined trend of the same is evidenced.

Comparison of IPO Performance Based on Categories

Normality check of dependent variables i.e. volatility indicates that data are not normal. To compare the performance based on company, issue, and market-specific variables, non-Parametric tests such as the Mann-Whitney U test and Kruskal- Wallis test is applied. Results of the same are depicted in Table-4.

Table-3 : Volatility Performance of SME IPOs

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Vol	187	0.00	0.38	0.08	0.07
Vol_10	187	0.00	0.13	0.05	0.03
Vol_20	187	0.00	0.09	0.04	0.02
Vol_30	187	0.00	0.08	0.04	0.02

Source : Compliance by the Author.

Volatility indicated the variation of share price, measured as the natural log of high to low price ratio, Table-4 depicts the comparison of volatility for the different categories, represents mean for each quartile and p-value (significance value) of Krushkal Wallis or Mann Whitney U test.

Detail study of Table-4 indicates IPOs with higher RNOW resulted in higher volatility. The highest volatility of 20 and 30 days of the listing results for IPOs falling highest RNOW quartile (Q4). Here, the difference is statistically significant for Vol_20 and Vol_30. Higher RNOW signals the higher future prospect of the firm thereby increasing the price, resulting in higher volatility.

IPOs with higher levels of subscription result in higher volatility. Volatility for 10, 20, and 30 days post listing resulted significantly highest with quartile (Q4) than other quartiles. Higher subscription during IPOs results in higher demand by investors who failed to get allotment. Results in higher demand lead to higher volatility in the price of the shares.

Positive market sentiment resulted significantly higher for vol_10, vol_20, and vol_30. The positive market condition leads to an increase in demand of investors in the secondary market for the initial days of listing, resulting in higher liquidity. Higher price volatility during the initial phase of listing for IPO stocks resulted from the higher liquidity.

Age, CFO_TA, PIPH, DE, Share premium, listing delay, a number of risk factors, offer size, lead manager prestige, method of pricing reported insignificantly different volatility for listing day, 10, 20, and 30 days from listing.

Conclusion

Volatility ratio on the listing day ratio found 0.08 which is in the declining trend up to 1-month post listing. Price variation is found to be very low, thereby age,

Table-4 : Volatility of SME IPOs Based on Different Categories

Variable	Category	No. IPOs	Vol	P value Vol	Vol_10	P value Vol_10	Vol_20	P value Vol_20	Vol_30	P value Vol_30
Company Specific Variables										
Age	Q1	47	0.08	0.329	0.05	0.425	0.04	0.257	0.04	0.159
	Q2	47	0.07		0.04		0.04		0.03	
	Q3	46	0.09		0.04		0.03		0.03	
	Q4	47	0.08		0.05		0.04		0.04	
CFO_TA	Q1	47	0.07	0.519	0.05	0.411	0.04	0.411	0.04	0.323
	Q2	47	0.08		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q3	46	0.08		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q4	47	0.10		0.06		0.05		0.05	
PIPH	Q1	47	0.08	0.465	0.05	0.425	0.04	0.697	0.04	0.867
	Q2	47	0.09		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q3	46	0.08		0.06		0.05		0.04	
	Q4	47	0.08		0.05		0.05		0.04	
RNOW	Q1	47	0.08	0.248	0.05	0.27	0.04	0.012**	0.04	0.004***
	Q2	47	0.09		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q3	46	0.09		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q4	47	0.07		0.06		0.05		0.05	
DE	Q1	47	0.08	0.855	0.05	0.511	0.05	0.467	0.04	0.702
	Q2	47	0.08		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q3	46	0.08		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q4	47	0.08		0.05		0.04		0.04	
Issue Specific Variables										
Share Premium	Q1	47	0.09	0.278	0.05	0.905	0.04	0.701	0.04	0.597
	Q2	47	0.08		0.05		0.05		0.04	
	Q3	46	0.07		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q4	47	0.09		0.05		0.04		0.04	

Listing Delay	Q1	47	0.07	0.266	0.05	0.448	0.04	0.826	0.04	0.665
	Q2	47	0.09		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q3	46	0.09		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q4	47	0.09		0.06		0.05		0.04	
Risk Factors	Q1	47	0.10	0.302	0.05	0.203	0.05	0.468	0.04	0.5
	Q2	47	0.08		0.06		0.05		0.04	
	Q3	46	0.07		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q4	47	0.08		0.05		0.04		0.04	
Subscription Times	Q1	47	0.05	0.000***	0.04	0.000***	0.04	0.000***	0.03	0.001***
	Q2	47	0.09		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q3	46	0.10		0.06		0.05		0.04	
	Q4	47	0.08		0.06		0.05		0.05	
Offer Size	Q1	47	0.08	0.867	0.05	0.961	0.04	0.836	0.04	0.512
	Q2	47	0.08		0.05		0.04		0.04	
	Q3	46	0.08		0.05		0.05		0.04	
	Q4	47	0.08		0.05		0.04		0.04	
Market Related Variables										
Market Sentiment	Positive	113	0.08	0.594	0.05	0.007***	0.05	0.005***	0.04	0.008***
	Negative	74	0.08		0.04		0.04		0.04	

*, **, *** indicate significance at 10 %, 5 % and 1 % level respectively

Source : *Compilation of Author.*

CFO_TA, PIPH, DE, Share premium, listing delay, a number of risk factors, offer size, lead manager prestige, method of pricing reported insignificantly different volatility for listing day, 10, 20 and 30 days from listing. IPOs with higher RNOW (Q4), higher level of subscription ratio (Q4), and IPOs issued during positive market sentiment resulted in higher volatility.

Implications and Future Scope of Study

Comparative analysis of IPO aid in understanding its nature of it and assist in better decision-making for primary market investors. The scope of the study is limited in twofold: one is in terms of its coverage to SME IPOs listed on NSE Emerge only and the other is the only comparison. The future researcher can delimit the same by extending the study to explore the factors responsible for the difference of performance of IPO based on the above categories.

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